

The Data Mine at Purdue University: Building a Collaborative Data Science Pipeline

Introduction

[The Data Mine](#) at [Purdue University](#) was established in the fall of 2018 with the goal of providing undergraduate students with hands-on research experience in data science at partner organizations across the country. The program was initially supported by a National Science Foundation (NSF) grant ([Award #2123321](#)) that funded 20 sophomore students per year over a five-year period. Since its inception, The Data Mine has evolved into a sustainable, soft-funded program that now connects graduate students, undergraduate students, faculty, and industry partners through mutually beneficial research projects.

Program Structure

The Data Mine is situated within the Purdue University's Office of the Provost and is designed to train undergraduate and graduate students across all majors to work in teams to create data-driven solutions to real-world problems. Undergraduate students are strongly encouraged to live in a designated residence space, although shared residence is not required.

In the NSF-funded predecessor to The Data Mine, sophomore undergraduate students worked with faculty through the summer on data-intensive research projects. Faculty mentors benefitted from working with talented students who applied their fresh perspectives and data science skills to research problems. Students received individualized guidance and a \$10,000 stipend including funding for research-related travel. See Gundlach & Ward (2021) to learn more about the history of the program.¹

Today, the Data Mine is fully supported by millions of dollars of grants and sponsorships and is open to graduate and undergraduate students of all levels and majors. In Fall 2025, approximately 2,500 students across the U.S., at Purdue and beyond. The Data Mine [team](#)

¹ Gundlach, E., & Ward, M. D. (2021). The Data Mine: Enabling Data Science Across the Curriculum. *Journal of Statistics and Data Science Education*, 29(sup1), S74–S82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691898.2020.1848484>

includes 22 staff members, including at least six roles that are dedicated to outreach and support for the [Corporate Partners Program](#).

PROJECT DETAILS:

- **Eligibility:** Open to all students, from first-year undergraduates to senior-level undergraduate students, and to all graduate students from any major. International students are eligible to participate. Although rare, some partners may impose restrictions to comply with regulations.
- **Projects:** Students select a [project](#) based on their interests.
- **Project management:** Students work in teams. Corporate mentors, Data Mine staff, and TA work collaboratively, using Agile methodologies, to plan and manage projects.
- **Duration:** Projects span the academic year (9 months). Undergraduates enroll in a 1-credit seminar each semester; this is optional for graduate students. Undergraduate and graduate students earn 3-credits per semester if they participate in the Corporate Partners program.
- **Mentorship:** Students receive guidance from their corporate partner mentor and Data Mine Teaching Assistant (TA) which are often undergraduate students with experience working with The Data Mine on contracts.
- **Symposium:** At the end of spring, students present their projects at [The Corporate Partners Symposium](#), with corporate partners reviewing final outputs to ensure proprietary information is not disclosed.

Partnership Development

The Corporate Partners program has been a cornerstone of The Data Mine since its inception. Partnerships are often initiated through alumni networks, word of mouth, and industry leaders learning about the program's impact.

STRATEGIES FOR PARTNERSHIP DEVELOPMENT:

- Keep discussions brief and focused on carefully listening for the company's challenges and needs, informed by pre-meeting research (e.g., earnings reports, fiscal year priorities, economic development publications, strategic reports, conferences, on-site meetings, etc.).
- Prioritize in-person meetings and personalized attention over electronic communication and recycled presentations.
- Emphasize ROI in terms of hours saved, efficiencies gained, or adoption of novel technologies.
- Use confidentiality agreements signed by students to build trust.
- Use a [Sponsor Acknowledgement](#) that covers up to 5 years of projects.
- Provide quick turnaround: proposals and project scopes are often developed within a single day of initial discussions.

PROCESS AT A GLANCE

1. Initial outreach or introduction (via alumni, faculty, or industry contacts; leveraging LinkedIn; partnerships with adjacent teams; referrals).
2. Needs-focused meeting and project scoping.
3. Submission of [sponsorship acknowledgement form](#) and [project charter](#).
4. Mentor orientation and Title IX training.
5. Projects typically launch at the start of the academic year in the fall.

KEY RESOURCES AND SUPPORT:

- Dedicated partnership-facing staff to conduct outreach and onboard partners.
- TAs who serve as liaisons between students and corporate mentors.
- Faculty and data science technical staff who provide subject matter expertise.
- Grants from federal, state, and philanthropic institutions.
- Contracts with a wide variety of Corporate Partners across several domains (e.g., aerospace; agriculture; manufacturing; pharmaceutical science).

Student Preparation

Students receive structured preparation during seminars and in training sessions led by staff data scientists, faculty, and Corporate Partners, to ensure productive collaborations with industry. Topics include:

- Professionalism and confidentiality training, including the use of secure cloud environments for sensitive data.
- Agile project management training and implementation in cross-disciplinary teams.
- Teaching Assistants as guides, bridging expectations and communication between students and corporate partners.
- Presentations during two-week Agile sprints, to develop communication and presentation skills, culminating in a Corporate Partners Symposium at the end of the academic year.

This preparation equips students with technical and interpersonal skills which are essential in professional environments.

Benefits & Outcomes

The Data Mine has generated significant benefits for students, faculty, and partner organizations:

- **For students:** Opportunities to engage in cross-disciplinary research, build professional networks, manage projects using industry-standard practices, and contribute to publications.

- **For faculty:** Professional development opportunities, insights into business problems to inform research and curriculum, and experience mentoring students from disciplines outside their department.
- **For industry partners:** Access to talented students and faculty, solutions to precompetitive challenges, and measurable ROI on projects.
- **For Purdue:** Positive reputation as an innovative institution that prepares talented graduates to collaborate and push the boundaries of data science to improve society.

Challenges & Future Directions

The Data Mine has faced challenges in scaling its operations and navigating the COVID-19 pandemic. Lessons learned include:

- Hiring talented staff and cultivating a collaborative team culture.
- Balancing oversight with autonomy to support innovation.
- Building trust with corporate partners through transparency and consistent delivery.

Future Directions:

- Strengthen inter-university collaborations to address large-scale industry needs and expand opportunities for students.
- Diversify funding sources to reduce vulnerability to short-term funding cycles.
- Continue refining student preparation to meet evolving industry demands.

Practical Guidance for Program Leaders

Program leaders looking to replicate The Data Mine's success should consider:

1. **Align student training with industry needs:** Ensure that students gain technical and professional skills relevant to employers, such as project management and communication.
2. **Establish a clear, repeatable process for onboarding industry partners:** Develop standardized forms, agreements, and timelines that make it easy for companies to scope projects and recruit students.
3. **Invest in face-to-face relationship-building with industry contacts:** Demonstrate commitment by traveling to meet partners, engaging in coffee chats, and listening carefully to their needs without relying on slide decks.
4. **Cultivate a trusted team culture with strong mentorship and open communication:** Invest in staff and leadership development and create a culture where team members feel valued and supported. A strong internal culture translates to better experiences for students and partners.
5. **Leverage alumni networks for partnership opportunities:** Alumni often serve as the first point of contact with potential partners. Involving alumni strengthens program sustainability and credibility with industry.

6. **Track and communicate ROI for partners to ensure long-term engagement:** Work with companies to define expected outcomes such as efficiency gains and revisit these outcomes after project completion.

Contact

For program inquiries, contact Mark Daniel Ward, the Director of The Data Mine, at mdw@purdue.edu.

Suggested Citation

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